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Wind Economic Analysis Project: An Alaska Case Study for Integration of High-Penetration Wind Energy in a Western Alaska Community

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Acronyms

ACEP	Alaska Center for Energy and Power
EV	Electric Vehicle
HOMER	Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources
USD	United States Dollar
kWh	kilowatt hour
AVEC	Alaska Village Electric Cooperative
COP	Coefficient of Performance
GMR	Geometric Mean Radius
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
kV	kilovolt
NPV	Net Present Value
ANTHC	Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium
AWOS	Automated Weather Observing System
MET	Meteorological evaluation tower
EWT	Emergya Wind Technologies
LoRaWAN	Long range wide area network

Executive Summary

Remote Alaskan communities face many challenges regarding energy production. Many of these communities are not part of an interconnected grid network and must operate their own electric microgrids. The isolation of these island microgrids mean they are subject to the extremely high costs of transporting fuel and materials, infrastructure maintenance and upgrades, and specialized labor. However, especially with the introduction of new sources of federal funding aid, many of these communities are looking into integrating renewable energy sources into their microgrids to mitigate the high cost of fuel. Many coastal regions in Alaska boast a strong wind resource that can be utilized to provide energy throughout both the summer and winter seasons. This report studies the economic feasibility of implementing a wind turbine with an installed capacity of one megawatt in small communities with high wind resources, with the focus being how to feasibly utilize the excess energy that such a relatively large wind turbine would produce compared to the communities' current electrical loads. One-megawatt wind turbines can be cost effective in larger rural communities such as St. Mary's and Stebbins, although the economics become much more challenging in many of the smaller communities. The difference is primarily the size of the electric load, which is larger for these bigger communities, partly because many of them are intertied to another village.

Information available for a representative community in western Alaska was used to model the integration of a large wind turbine. The study utilizes the grid-modeling software HOMER in conjunction with data on wind speeds, temperature and energy consumption from the community to simulate its grid structure and behavior. The chosen wind turbine and supporting infrastructure were integrated into the simulated microgrid to gauge how the turbine would affect the energy production and consumption. Using this simulated data, a number of proposed community infrastructure changes were analyzed to determine the most economically and efficiently feasible combination. The supporting technologies studied for their ability to economically integrate high levels of wind generation in the small community were grid-scale Lithium-ion storage batteries, electrification of community vehicles with managed charging, and electrification of heating with dispatchability of this load.

It was found that residential electric resistance space heaters using thermal storage controlled by utilities added the most total net present value to the community as a whole from the use of excess wind energy. Replacing the gas tribal SUVs and privately owned ATVs with electric versions of these vehicles resulted in a higher net present value per kWh of excess wind-generated energy, but used a much smaller amount of this excess. Using both of these proposed implementations along with economically-sized grid storage batteries was not enough to result in a net present value positive project. However, when adding in tax credits from the Inflation Reduction Act and the clean vehicle tax credit and accounting for the avoided costs of bulk fuel storage the net present value of the project is positive with a benefit to cost ratio of nearly 1.4.

This study details some methods that remote communities might use to more cost-effectively integrate high-penetration renewable energy projects. By maximizing the use of locally produced renewable energy, the dependence of the community on shipped-in diesel and community and household emissions are minimized. The costs of future bulk fuel storage upgrades for the community and risks from local storage of fuel may also be reduced by significantly reducing the annual consumption of fuel.

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1 Introduction

Many communities in rural Alaska are pursuing renewable energy technologies as a way to mitigate the extremely high energy costs they face. While there is currently a once-in-a-generation opportunity to construct renewable energy infrastructure with funding available through the Bipartisan Infrastructure Law and Inflation Reduction Act, a variety of challenges need to be overcome to secure this funding and successfully implement renewable projects, including high capital costs and integration challenges.

Unlike most of the United States, communities in remote Alaska typically operate their own diesel-powered isolated microgrids, leading to a variety of challenges. This leads to high capital costs for new infrastructure due to a lack of economies of scale. Construction costs are also increased by the expense of logistics and transportation of materials and specialized labor to communities that are only accessible via summer barges or multiple airplane flights. Many of these microgrids also require significant infrastructure upgrades before they can successfully integrate the intermittent power produced by renewable technologies. Finally, the arctic and subarctic climates found in rural Alaska lead to significantly higher heating energy needs than other areas of the U.S. and these loads are more challenging to meet with renewable sources.

In many ways, wind power is an excellent option for remote communities in Alaska. Alaska has an abundant and strong wind resource that aligns well with many community locations. In contrast to other renewable resources such as solar, typical wind regimes also often match the winter peaking electric and heating loads of rural communities fairly well. Wind technology also has high adoption rates globally, which has led to a decrease in installed project costs of approximately 40% in the past decade and suggests that prices could continue to come down (despite a bump in costs for energy projects of all types in 2022 related to world events).

Wind technology also brings its own set of challenges. Wind is generally intermittent, which can make integration into small grids a challenge, especially since the exponential relationship between wind speed and power generation exacerbates the variation in power produced. Finally, wind turbine size is increasing globally, which raises concerns for long-term availability and support for the smaller 100-kW turbines that have primarily been installed in rural communities throughout Alaska.

This study aims to address many of the challenges discussed above by investigating the possibility of installing a larger (1-MW) wind turbine in a small community and then evaluating a variety of ways to use the excess renewable energy produced beyond what can be used to meet the community's electrical load, including battery energy storage systems, residential heating electrification, non-residential building heating electrification, and electric vehicles. This approach has the potential to improve the economics of wind projects by increasing the economies of scale of a project while at the same time addressing communities' heating and/or transportation needs.

2 Case Study

Alaska has approximately 240 remote communities which are isolated from major roadways and power grids. These islanded power systems are primarily powered by diesel generators and rely on long-distance fuel imports to the community. The costs associated with transportation and storage of diesel fuel results in high power generation costs.

The chosen community for this analysis is a rural, primarily Yup'ik community home to approximately 500 people in approximately 94 households[1]. It is located on the Yukon-Kuskokwim Delta. The community is not connected to a road system or major power grid. Access is primarily by plane or barge and power is generated locally at a diesel power plant.

This community was chosen for several reasons. Since the goal of this project is to evaluate the economics of installing a large wind turbine along with a suite of electrification options in a small community, it was important to select a community of the right size. Its population is significantly smaller than the next largest community with an EWT wind turbine of approximately 1-MW installed (Stebbins, whose grid serves approximately 1000 people [2]), but large enough to have a full school, water distribution system, and other energy needs. Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium (ANTHC) has also been working with the community on various energy projects and their leadership has expressed a desire to pursue renewable energy systems as a way to reduce the high cost of living in the community.

Data availability is also essential to producing meaningful results. The community had a wind measurement tower, also known as a meteorological evaluation tower (MET), installed between 2008 and 2014 which collected data that indicated it has a good wind resource (wind power class 4). Additionally, the community's power system is owned and operated by the Alaska Village Electric Cooperative (AVEC), which operates power systems in 57 communities [3] in rural Alaska and was able to provide 15-minute electric load data for the 2019 to 2022 study period. The community is also one of the 66 communities in Alaska with a National Weather Service Automated Weather Observing System (AWOS) station [4] and has sufficient data available to estimate heat loads of the school, water treatment plant, and residential buildings.

This case study investigates the techno-economic implications of using combinations of utility-scale battery energy storage systems (BESS), dispatchable electric heating systems, and deferrable electric vehicle charging to help integrate a large wind turbine in a similar community in Alaska.

3 Methods: HOMER

In this section the required data, the inputs for the models, as well as the employed methods for the power system and consumer-side economic modeling are presented.

HOMER Pro (hereafter referred to just as HOMER, but not to be confused with the HOMER Grid tool from the same vendor) [5] is a software tool for islanded power system energy balance and dispatch modeling [6]. HOMER allows a custom grid configuration, which requires the technical specifications of the different grid components, such as the generators (e.g. diesel generator, wind turbines), any storage capacity and the load data.

For this case study, all data used in the HOMER modeling was gathered or synthesized over three years. As mentioned previously, all gathered data from the community spans from September 2019 to September 2022. To have three full calendar years to work with, data from January to September 2022 was appended before September 2019 to create a synthesized 2019 year. With this data, three 1-year models were made covering “2019”, 2020 and 2021, variations of the models were created as additional loads and components were implemented.

Details of the data, HOMER components/configuration and other parameters modeled are given in the following sections

3.1 Controls

HOMER has two default microgrid dispatch controllers, Load Following and Cycle Charging [7]. These controllers affect how the battery and deferrable load are served. In Cycle Charging the energy storage is charged and discharged to keep as many of the running generators operating at maximum rated capacity as possible, leading to maximizing fuel efficiency. In Load Following the generator produces just enough energy to serve the loads, leading to increased fuel conservation. Load Following mode was chosen for consistency in all modeling runs as it was the preferable control mode when both a deferrable load (EVs) and a BESS system were both included, leading to economically optimized solutions.

3.2 Weather Data

An essential part of this analysis relies on accurate time series weather data. The analysis must consider the coincident temporal variation of wind speeds, temperatures, electric loads, and heating loads as this is essential to understanding how much of the modeled wind power production can be used to offset diesel power generation and whether or not any available excess power production can be utilized through storage or by meeting other loads. For this reason all weather data had to match the 2019 through 2022 time period of 15-minute electric load data provided by AVEC.

Two primary sources of data were used for the weather analysis: met tower data published by Doug Vaught of V3 Energy, LLC [8] and weather station data, including temperature and wind speed, from the National Weather Service station located at the community’s airport [9]. The 30 m tall MET was installed in the community at a location deemed ideal due to its wind exposure, road access, being out of the airport’s flight path, and short distance to connect to existing power distribution infrastructure. Data from the tower was collected starting in 2008 and ending in 2014 including a significant gap during this time when it was not functioning. The only calendar year that had complete data was 2013. Wind speed and temperature data from the PADM weather station was available inclusive of the years 2019 through 2022. To create simulated wind data for the preferred wind location that was temporally coincident with the load data, linear regression analysis was performed to find the correlation between the PADM data and the MET data that overlapped in time. This relationship was used on PADM data from 2019-2022 to simulate data at the MET site for this time period.

3.3 Electrical Load

The base load for the models was the community load as recorded and provided by AVEC over three years at 15 minute resolution. This load was set as a primary load in HOMER modeling, a load that the system must serve at all times. This load averages 4181.38 kWh/day, with a peak of 315.2kW in February in 2019 and 2020 and in November in 2021. The daily profile is typical of communities in Alaska with increased usage during the day and seasonally higher usage in the winter than the summer.

Two additional loads were used in modeling scenarios. The first of these was a residential electric heating load as detailed in **Section 4.2**. In HOMER modeling scenarios including this load it was set as a second primary load.

Electric vehicle (EV) electrification loads are further discussed in **Section 4.3**. These are modeled as a deferrable load in HOMER, a type of load that must be served, but has flexibility as to when this happens due to inherent storage. HOMER serves the deferrable load differently depending on which dispatch strategy is being used. When using the load following strategy, it will serve the deferrable load only when the grid is producing excess energy or when the storage capacity of the load is empty. When using the cycle charging strategy, it will follow the same serving strategy as load following, but will also serve the deferrable load when generators are operating and are able to produce more electricity than the primary load's need. As noted in 3.1.1, the Load Following control strategy was used in all models.

3.4 Diesel Generation

The community has three diesel generators in the power plant, as shown in Table 1, below (data supplied by AVEC).

Generator	Capacity (kW)	O&M Cost (\$/op. hour)
CAT 3456	505	5.00
Detroit Diesel S60K4 1800	360	3.24
Detroit Diesel S60K4c 1800	236	2.12

Table 1. List of the community's connected generators

The CAT generator was modeled with a closely matching CAT from the HOMER library. The two Detroit Diesel (DD) generators were implemented by modifying existing generators in the HOMER library using fuel curve data from AVEC. Lifetime hours and capital cost data from AVEC was also input into all three generator components.

The community's installed diesel generation capacity exceeds load requirements and the preference is to have no more than two generators running at the same time for redundancy.

The specific fuel consumption of the generators is determined by the generator efficiency, which in turn can vary depending on the operational loading of the generators (generators operating close to capacity are more efficient), which is reflected in the fuel curves and can be observed in figures A.1-A.3 in the appendix.

3.5 Wind Generation

The modeled turbine is an Emergya Wind Technologies (EWT) DW 61 one-MW turbine. This is similar to EWT turbines that have been successfully operated in communities in Alaska for over 13 years and is thus a trusted and available product. HOMER has a similar EWT turbine in its library, it was modified by inputting the power curve data sourced from the EWT DW61 power curve document [10]. The modeled wind turbine output is dependent on the weather data used in the model (**Section 4.2**). Cost estimates were entered for the turbine component's capital and operations cost. Assumptions about the turbine's maintenance schedule were entered based on information from Kotzebue Electric.

The power curve graph used in the modeling represents the relationship between wind speed and output power. This relationship is cubic before plateauing at the maximum power output of the turbine. The output power drops to zero if the wind speeds reach the turbine's cut-out limit. Wind turbines also have a cut-in speed, a minimum required wind speed for the turbine to start producing power. The DW 61 has a cut-in and cut-out speed of 3 m/s and 25 m/s respectively. Finally, the wind speed data was adjusted to the 46-meter hub height of the EWT wind turbine within HOMER using a wind shear power law exponent of 0.128 that was calculated in the V3 wind study.

3.6 Battery Energy Storage System

The battery energy storage system (BESS) consists of the battery and the converter. The sizing of these two components can be optimized via HOMER's optimizer or search space. HOMER's optimizer was initially used, but was found to under-optimize the BESS sizing, likely due to limitations of the algorithm. Using a search space from

100-800 kW for the battery and 100-600 kW for the converter in increments of 100 kW resulted in robust optimized sizing for the BESS in the base case. This size of BESS was then required in subsequent scenarios including the battery storage system, such as the EV and residential electric heating scenario, the sizing for the BESS for these scenarios is 400 kWh for the battery and 300 kW for the converter. The battery was modeled using HOMER's generic 1-kW Lithium ion module, no changes were made to the battery except for entering capital and O&M costs.

3.7 Base Case Scenario

The base case scenario consists of the community's three generators, the proposed wind turbine and the community load; this essentially models what the community's current power grid looks like with the addition of the wind turbine. This scenario was used to gauge how much excess energy the 1-MW turbine would theoretically produce. With this knowledge additional loads and components, such as BESS and the electric heating load, can be implemented into the system to utilize the excess energy. In a sense the base case scenario acts as a foundation for which an optimal power system can be found. This will be further discussed in **Section 4.4**.

4 Methods: Utilizing Excess Wind Energy

4.1 Prioritizing Uses of Excess Generation

Our analysis looked at a number of systems that utilize excess generation to provide useful services, such as space heating and electric vehicles. Most of the excess generation results from excess wind power – that is, wind power exceeding the standard electric utility load at the time. Some excess generation is also due to minimum loading requirements of the diesel gensets.

This excess generation is a limited resource. If one particular use of the excess is implemented, the excess generation resource is reduced, and less is available for other possible uses. A simplistic way to evaluate the solutions is to compare each use on how much net benefit (benefits - cost) the use creates per kWh of excess generation consumed. Those uses that provide the most value per kWh are likely to be the uses that should be prioritized.

Table 2 shows the excess generation use analyzed in this study, and the table shows the net present value generated per excess generation kWh/year utilized (all dollars in this report are 2023 inflation-adjusted dollars). More details on each of these options is presented in subsequent sections of the report. To get a sense of the absolute magnitude of value created, the table also shows the total net present value of implementing the option, assuming it is the only option implemented. Also, the upfront capital cost required to build the option is shown in the table. Our hope is that this table can provide general guidance towards prioritizing use of excess generation in other communities. However, a detailed analysis of each community should be performed before proceeding with project selection.

Category	Capital cost	Total NPV as only implemented measure (along with BESS)	NPV per kWh/year of excess wind
Residential heating electrification (controllable)	\$1,857,000	\$2,260,000	\$ 2.07/kWh/yr
Non-residential heating electrification: School (controllable)	\$775,000	-\$456,000	\$ -2.81/kWh/yr
Non-residential heating electrification: Water Treatment Plant (controllable)	\$275,000	-\$166,000	\$ -3.75/kWh/yr
Electric Vehicles (total replacement of Tribal SUVs & ATVs)	Total replacement cost: \$590,000	\$513,950	\$ 6.79/kWh/yr

Table 2. Upfront capital for each build option

As the table shows, the highest priority use for excess wind based on NPV per kWh is replacing Tribal SUVs with EVs combined with replacing all ATVs with electric models. These vehicles produce \$6.79 of net present value for every kWh/year of excess generation used. This result is based on replacing the EVs regardless of their age and assuming that there is no salvage value to the replaced gas vehicle. EV replacement can become more cost effective when replacing near-end-of-life gas vehicles where the NPV would be based on the cost differential between a new gas vehicle and the new electric one. The next most valuable use of excess wind is electrically heating residences with thermal storage heaters, an option that produces \$2.07 net present value for every kWh/year of excess generation used.

The following sections present more details on this modeling and the results of combinations of solutions.

4.2 Building Heating Loads

4.2.1 Goals

The goal of the Building Heating Loads analysis was to identify the “best” retrofit electric heating systems for community buildings that utilize excess electricity generation (predominantly wind power) from the AVEC electric system, assuming the installation of a 1-MW wind turbine on that electric system. “Best” was defined as the set of systems that maximize the net present value considering the heating fuel savings, the costs of building and operating the new heating systems, and the costs of any needed upgrades to the AVEC electric utility system.

The buildings included in the analysis were the residential homes in the community, the school, and the water treatment plant. For the residential homes, only the space heating load was addressed. The residential space heating load is estimated to be approximately ten times larger than the domestic hot water load, and therefore has the best potential to produce significant fuel savings. Efforts to use excess electricity generation to displace domestic hot water loads are also not likely to be cost-effective due to the relatively small size and dispersion of the load.

For the school and the water treatment plant, the retrofit electric heating system was assumed to integrate with and reduce the fuel use of the existing oil-fired boiler heating system. In those buildings, the oil boiler provides space heat, domestic water heat, and other process heat in the case of the water treatment plant (e.g. adding heating to piped circulating water distribution systems).

4.2.2 Methodology

The analysis of the three different building types – residential, school, and water treatment plant – were done separately, so that it could be determined whether retrofit electric heating systems for each building type increased or decreased net present value benefits. The analysis for each building type involved using the results from HOMER modeling runs, and then doing additional computations (using the Python programming language) outside of the HOMER modeling process. The HOMER runs provide hourly values for the amount of excess generation available on the electric system, the outdoor temperature for each hour (which affects space heating loads), the electric system demand, and how that demand is met through a combination of diesel generation, wind, and battery. These values were then used by the Python model to determine the performance of the electric heating system for the building, the amount of heating fuel saved by the electric heating system, and the addition to the load on the AVEC utility system.

Heating fuel savings were translated to fuel dollar savings. Additions to electric load were used to determine increased peak loading on the electric distribution system, increased peak loading on the diesel generator system, and additions to diesel generator fuel use, for the portions of the added electric load that forced more diesel use. AVEC Engineering provided estimates of the electric utility system upgrade costs that would be incurred to support any increases in these peak demand components. Note that not all retrofit heating systems analyzed added to the AVEC diesel generator usage. Some systems were assumed to be centrally controlled by the utility to only operate during periods of excess generation and to not exceed the amount of excess generation available.

The HOMER model runs that were used in the analysis included the 1-MW wind turbine and a battery energy storage system, appropriately sized for the system. Actual electric load and weather data were available for the HOMER model for three years: 2019, 2020, and 2021. All three years of model runs were used in the building heating load analysis, and the final results and conclusions were based on the average across the three years of analysis.

For the electric heating systems analyzed (detailed further in the next section), the maximum capacity for each system was chosen to approximately optimize economic net benefit; the systems were not sized to meet peak heating load of the buildings. Thus, it was assumed that the existing heating system in the building continues to operate and provide supplemental heat to the retrofit electric heating system. This approach moderates the impact on the utility electric system, and improves the net benefit of the retrofit heating system. A large fraction of the annual heating load can be met by a system sized to only meet 50 - 75% of the peak heating load.

As discussed in the following section, a number of different possible residential electric heating systems were analyzed. Some of those systems included a heat pump. When modeling the use of the heat pump, it was assumed that the heat pump was only utilized during the period March 10 - December 1 of each year, avoiding the coldest winter weather period. This operating approach is consistent with that used for the numerous heat pump installations in the Northwest Arctic Borough. For determining the efficiency of the heat pump while operating, the algorithm used

in the Alaska Mini-Split Heat Pump Calculator [11] was used. This algorithm determines the heat pump efficiency based on outdoor temperature, with colder temperatures resulting in poorer efficiency.

Some of the included residential heating options used a thermal storage electric heater, equivalent to the Steffes 2106 model [12]. An idealized thermal storage heater model was built that assumes that the electric input power supplies the current heat output of the heater (6 kW maximum), and additional input power can be supplied to charge the thermal storage up to a combined maximum of 9 kW. The maximum thermal storage for the heater is 40 kWh.

4.2.3 Modeling Inputs

In this section, the important input values for the Building Heating Load analysis are presented.

Residential Buildings

For the residential analysis, it was assumed that of the 94 occupied residences in the community, 90% participate in an electric heating retrofit. Each participating building was treated as having the same heating load, which was estimated from data in the Alaska Housing Finance Corporation 2014 Housing Assessment [1]. The space heating load was modeled with a building balance point temperature of 60 degrees Fahrenheit and a heat loss coefficient of 476 BTU/hour/degree (F). Further, it was assumed that the existing oil-fired heating system in these homes operated at an efficiency of 78%.

Seven different retrofit electric heating systems were analyzed. Some of these systems involved heaters that are centrally controlled by the utility to only operate during periods of excess generation, and to limit their demand in aggregate to the amount of excess generation. Other systems involve no central control so will at times add to the electric load served by AVEC diesel generation. Some of the seven systems are a combination of the two above types. For example, one system model assumes an uncontrolled mini-split heat pump combined with 6 kW of electric heaters that are controlled to operate during periods of excess generation.

Table 3 describes and shows the cost characteristics of the seven residential electric heating systems analyzed.

System Name	Description	Upgrade Cost per Building	Utility Distribution Upgrade Cost	Utility Generation Upgrade Cost	Utility Control / Communication Costs	Total Capital Costs based on 84.6 Homes	Replacement Costs for Building Upgrades
Heat Pump	12K single-head mini-split heat pump, one per home	\$10,000	\$367,000	\$1,500,000	\$0	\$2,713,000	\$5,000/home every 10 years
Heat Pump + Electric	12K mini-split + 4 x 1.5 kW wall-mounted, plug-in electric space heaters w/ no utility control.	\$11,500	\$611,474	\$10,000,000	\$0	\$11,584,374	\$5,400/home every 10 years
Heat Pump + Controlled Electric	12K mini-split + utility-controlled 4 x 1.5 kW wall-mounted, plug-in, space heaters. LoRaWAN Smart Plug for control.	\$12,000	\$611,474	\$1,500,000	\$200,000	\$3,326,674	\$5,600/home every 10 years
Controlled Electric	Utility-controlled 4 x 1.5 kW wall-mounted, plug-in space heaters. LoRaWAN Smart Plug control.	\$2,000	\$519,796	\$0	\$200,000	\$888,996	\$600/home every 10 years
Electric	4 x 1.5 kW wall-mounted, plug-in electric space heaters w/ no utility control.	\$1,500	\$519,796	\$10,000,000	\$0	\$10,646,696	\$400/home every 10 years
Controlled Thermal Storage	One 240VAC 9 kW input, 6 kW heat output, 40 kWh thermal storage heater. Utility-controlled.	\$12,000	\$642,033	\$0	\$200,000	\$1,857,233	\$2,000/home every 15 years
Controlled Thermal Storage + Heat Pump	Thermal storage heater as above + 12K single-head mini-split heat pump.	\$21,000	\$734,000	\$1,500,000	\$200,000	\$4,210,600	\$6,000/home every 10 years

* Highlighted row is the chosen Residential Heating System.

Table 3. Cost characteristics of the seven residential electric heating systems

The “Upgrade Cost per Building” column in Table 3 shows the estimated retrofit cost for each home. The cost for periodic replacement of heating components in the home is estimated in the furthest right column: “Replacement Costs for Building Upgrades”. Three columns address the needed upgrades to the AVEC utility system to support the electric heating systems. The “Utility Distribution Upgrade Cost” accounts for needed upgrades to transformers in the AVEC electric distribution system. For electric heating systems that add to diesel generation peak demand, the “Utility Generation Upgrade Cost” estimates the needed upgrade cost of the AVEC diesel generation plant. Both of these utility costs were determined from communication with AVEC Engineering staff. Finally, “Utility Control / Communication Costs” cover the cost of additional software and control hardware necessary for controlling heaters that are only meant to operate during periods of excess generation. These estimates were guided by an estimate of the utility software required for a controllable electric boiler project in Nome.

A number of these residential heating systems use heaters that are controlled by the utility. The two different heaters that are used are: 1) a thermal storage heater equivalent to the Steffes 2106, which has 9 kW maximum input (requiring a dedicated 240V circuit), 6 kW maximum heat output, and 40 kWh of thermal storage, and 2) four 1.5 kW wall-mounted, plug-in, electric resistance heaters, controlled by wireless LoRaWAN Smart Plugs. The thermal storage heater system has the ability to be controlled by the utility through a Power Line Carrier transceiver. Custom software will still be required to dispatch the heaters during periods of excess generation.

The controlled, plug-in electric heater system contemplates use of a LoRaWAN wireless network [13] to allow AVEC to control the heaters. Off-the-shelf LoRaWAN Smart Plugs (< \$100 each) would be utilized to switch on and off each heater. LoRaWAN has seen widespread use in Alaska to monitor water treatment plants and other facilities. However, this application of LoRaWAN has not been used before. Custom software would be required to implement the application. The following Results section (**Section 4.2.4**) shows that the plug-in electric heater system controlled by LoRaWAN Smart Plugs resulted in the maximum net present value of the seven systems analyzed. However, due to the untested status of that solution, the controlled thermal storage heater was chosen as the system to include in the final results of this study.

Non-Residential Buildings

Two non-residential buildings were separately analyzed to determine the benefits and costs of electric heating retrofits: the school and the water treatment plant. Heating load characteristics from these buildings were determined from energy audit data. The existing oil-fired boilers in these buildings serve space heating, domestic hot water and process loads. These were converted into monthly heat load coefficients (BTU/hour per degree Fahrenheit, assuming a balance point of 65°F). Because loads are not just for space heating, these coefficients exhibit noticeable variation across months. These coefficients were then used to calculate hourly heat loads consistent with the hourly HOMER model runs. Table 4 shows the monthly coefficients for both buildings.

Heat Loss Coefficient		
BTU/hour / deg-F, 65 deg-F balance point		
Month	Water Treatment Plant	School
1	1,049	4,296
2	1,133	4,202
3	1,200	5,338
4	1,526	4,872
5	1,421	5,022
6	1,440	6,309
7	2,043	5,746
8	1,471	4,657
9	1,021	3,628
10	973	3,848
11	1,213	3,519
12	1,078	4,398

Table 4. Monthly coefficients for Water Treatment and School

The audits also indicated existing oil heating efficiencies of 83.5% for the school and 69.3% for the water treatment plant. These were used in the analysis.

Only one type of electric heating system was modeled for each of these buildings. The electric heating system was assumed to be an electric boiler that is controlled by AVEC to operate only during periods of excess generation. During those periods, the electric boiler would have priority over the existing oil boiler, but the oil boiler would make up any heating load needs beyond the capacity of the electric boiler.

Table 5 shows the costs that were estimated for the two electric boiler installations, including associated utility system upgrade costs. These costs were based on estimates for similar projects estimated by the ANTHC Engineering department. The School building upgrade cost already includes the cost of a new utility transformer, explaining the zero cost shown in the Utility Distribution Upgrade Cost column. For the Water Treatment Plant, the existing transformer is expected to be large enough to support the additional 25 kW load of the electric boiler.

Building Type	System Name	Description	Upgrade Cost per Building	Utility Distribution Upgrade Cost	Utility Generation Upgrade Cost	Utility Control / Communication Costs	Total Capital Costs	Replacement Costs for Building Upgrades
School	Electric Boiler	Utility-controlled 100 kW Electric Boiler to preheat existing boiler, includes utility transformer	\$600,000	\$0	\$0	\$175,000	\$775,000	\$100,000 every 20 years
Water Treatment Plant	Electric Boiler	Utility-controlled 25 kW Electric Boiler to preheat existing boiler.	\$100,000	\$0	\$0	\$175,000	\$275,000	\$20,000 every 20 years

Table 5. Summarized results of non-residential building analysis

4.2.4 Results Residential Results

Table 6 summarizes the results of modeling the seven residential electric heat systems. They are ranked in the table in order of Net Present Value, which is the sum across the 25 year study period of the heating fuel savings minus the sum of the costs of each solution, expressed in economic present value terms. The “Controlled Electric” system (four 1.5 kW plug-in electric heaters controlled by LoRaWAN Smart Plugs) had the highest net present value, but because of the untested nature of that solution, the second highest system, “Controlled Thermal Storage” was selected as the winning residential system.

System Name	Net Present Value, \$	Heating Fuel Saved, gal / year	Heating Fuel Cost Saved, \$ / year	Increase in Diesel Generation Peak Demand, kW	Increase in Diesel Generation, MWh / year	Excess Generation Used, MWh / year	Net Present Value per kWh/year of Excess Generation Used
Controlled Electric	\$2,408,995	26,089	\$217,061	0	0	863	\$2.75
Controlled Thermal Storage	\$2,259,519	32,328	\$268,969	0	0	1,069	\$2.07
Heat Pump + Controlled Electric	\$1,910,665	58,301	\$485,066	184	407	684	\$2.76
Controlled Thermal Storage + Heat Pump	\$1,390,042	61,370	\$510,595	184	407	786	\$1.73
Heat Pump	\$681,454	43,095	\$358,548	184	407	182	\$3.66
Heat Pump + Electric	-\$8,369,771	86,658	\$720,996	712	1,345	684	-\$12.57
Electric	-\$9,757,396	83,556	\$695,190	539	1,900	863	-\$11.75

Table 6. Summarized results of seven modeled residential electric heating systems

The numeric columns of Table 6 show selected key results from the modeling. The two building “Heating Fuel” columns give annual fuel savings in gallons and dollars resulting from use of the electric heating system. The “In-

crease in Diesel Generation Peak Demand kW” column displays how much the peak loading on the AVEC diesel generation system is increased by the electric heating system. Systems that only run during excess generation periods show a zero in this column. “Increase in Diesel Generation, MWh/year” indicates the annual addition of diesel generation needed to support the electric heat system. Again, some systems impose no additional generation requirement. “Excess Generation Used, MWh/year” indicates how much “free” excess generation is used by the electric heating system. Finally, the “Net Present Value per kWh/year of Excess Generation Used” is a ranking metric that shows how much net value the heating system provides per annual kWh of excess generation used by the system. This metric is a good way to rank alternative and competing uses of excess generation.

The modeling results above assume that these electric heating solutions are implemented in isolation, without any competing uses of the utility excess generation (although, a BESS system was included in the baseline reference case). The final results of this study do consider a combination of multiple excess generation uses (specifically, residential heating and electric vehicles) and properly account for the limited amount of excess generation available to these uses.

Note that five of the seven alternative electric heating systems showed a positive net present value, meaning they had more benefits than costs. Any of these five would be beneficial to implement, however the top systems provide the most benefits and should be favored. The top two options provide about \$2.3 million of net benefit, which is available to help justify the costs of the wind turbine and utility battery upgrade.

Electric utility upgrade costs were a very important factor in this analysis. The systems that performed the worst economically (the bottom of the list) did so due to their large impact on the AVEC utility system. For example, the “Electric” system, which involved adding 6 kW of electric heat to each residence without central control by AVEC added 540 kW to the peak diesel generation needs. AVEC Engineering indicated that a large addition like that would require a \$10 million changeout of the diesel generation plant. The top two systems in the table have no impacts on the AVEC generation plant and relatively minor impacts on the AVEC distribution plant (primarily transformer upgrades). Refer to Table 3 to examine all of these utility cost impacts in detail.

A sensitivity analysis was done that examined the impact of receiving an \$8,000 / home tax credit for heating systems that include a heat pump. Under the current Inflation Reduction Act rules, the \$8,000 credit is only available to low-income households, but for simplicity and to investigate the maximum possible impact, the credit was applied to all homes. With this capital cost reduction, the “Heat Pump + Controlled Electric” system moved to the top of the Net Present Value sort, but it only surpassed the next best option by about 6%.

The prior results were based on access to all of the available excess generation resulting from the AVEC utility system configured with a wind turbine and BESS. After doing the ranking of various possible uses of excess generation, it was determined that the most valuable use was converting Tribal SUVs and the ATVs in the community to EVs. The EVs do use some of the available excess generation, so it was important to re-evaluate the Residential heating options after removal of this excess generation. Table 7 summarizes the results of this analysis. The amount of excess generation used by the EVs is relatively small; the net present value for the best heating systems drops by about 10% due to having less excess wind available. The Controlled Thermal Storage option is still the preferred option, and numeric results from Table 7 for that option are moved forward to the final economic results of this study.

System Name	Net Present Value, \$	Heating Fuel Saved, gal / year	Heating Fuel Cost Saved, \$ / year	Increase in Diesel Generation Peak Demand, kW	Increase in Diesel Generation, MWh / year	Excess Generation Used, MWh / year	Net Present Value per kWh/year of Excess Generation Used
Controlled Electric	\$2,215,340	24,709	\$205,579	0	0	817	\$2.67
Controlled Thermal Storage	\$2,030,387	30,695	\$255,383	0	0	1,015	\$1.95
Heat Pump + Controlled Electric	\$1,749,510	57,490	\$478,314	184	418	646	\$2.67
Controlled Thermal Storage + Heat Pump	\$1,212,928	60,444	\$502,896	184	418	744	\$1.59
Heat Pump	\$634,169	43,095	\$358,548	184	418	170	\$3.62
Heat Pump + Electric	-\$8,530,763	86,658	\$720,996	714	1,383	646	-\$13.58
Electric	-\$9,950,774	83,556	\$695,190	540	1,946	817	-\$12.67

Table 7. Summarized results of seven modeled residential electric heating systems after removal of excess energy generation used by EV vehicles

Non-Residential Results

Similar results for the two Non-Residential buildings are shown in Table 8.

Building	Net Present Value, \$	Heating Fuel Saved, gal / year	Heating Fuel Cost Saved, \$ / year	Increase in Diesel Generation Peak Demand, kW	Increase in Diesel Generation, MWh / year	Excess Generation Used, MWh / year	Net Present Value per kWh/year of Excess Generation Used
School	-\$455,645	4,432	\$23,044	0	0	174	-\$2.81
Water Treatment Plant	-\$166,423	1,873	\$9,738	0	0	48	-\$3.75

Table 8. Summarized results of non-residential building analysis

For both the School and the Water Treatment Plant, the net present value of implementing electric heating is shown to be negative, i.e. the costs exceed the benefits on a present value basis. This is primarily due to the high installed costs of the electric boilers. These specialized, remote projects incur substantial costs beyond the cost of the equipment.

Because these two projects showed negative net benefits, they are not included in the final set of projects included in the economic analysis.

4.3 Electric Vehicles Modeling

The EV loads used in the HOMER modeling were created using a modified version of ACEP's EV calculator [14]. This calculator is a Python program that takes in the driving profiles, for both summer and winter, of the vehicles that can be found in the community. A driving profile, in miles per day, was estimated for vehicle types in the community based on road distances in town. Using this information, the engine behind the calculator [15] creates a daily energy use by summing three temperature dependent terms: energy used to drive, parked energy use to condition the battery, and energy used to idle (or keep warm while parked). This calculator was modified to model ATVs and snow machines in addition to cars and trucks, and was further modified to output the monthly energy use.

Based on a site visit to the community there are approximately 12 household SUVs and pickup trucks in town. Additionally, there is approximately one ATV and one snow machine per household. There are also estimated to be two SUVs owned by the tribe to be used in a transport service to the clinic and airport. They are assumed to be driven 40 miles per day on weekdays and 20 miles per day on weekends with 240 minutes of warm idle time. SUVs are modeled with the same efficiency as trucks. Household trucks, ATVs and snow machines are assumed to be driven 4 miles per day with 30 minutes of warm idle time. Snow machines are assumed to be operated seasonally

from October 1 to May 1, however it is assumed that the battery requires energy for conditioning any time temperatures are below 20°F.

The storage capacity for each vehicle is modeled as 100 kWh for each truck/SUV, 23 kWh for snow machines, and 11 kWh for ATVs. This total storage capacity was used as an input for the EV deferrable load in HOMER modeling and was adjusted in accordance with the level for electrification; at full electrification of the community vehicle fleet the total capacity was 2964 kWh, while the Tribal SUV + ATV electrification (swapping out only the two tribal SUVs and all community ATVs for electric vehicles) had a capacity of 706kWh.

The peak load for the EVs was also adjusted in accordance to the level of electrification depending on the number of chargers that would be integrated into the grid system. The chargers have three levels modeled at: level 1 (L1) 120V at 1 kW, level 2 (L2) 240V at 10 kW, and level 3 (L3) DC fast chargers at 50 kW. The peak load input for modeling the EVs as a deferrable load in HOMER ranged from 196 kW at full electrification (46 L1, 10 L2, 1 L3 chargers) down to 66 kW at Tribal SUV + ATV electrification (46 L1 and 2 L2 chargers). A number of each type of charger was chosen based on household and community needs for keeping vehicles charged, maximizing the amount of excess wind that could be used for charging the fleet, while minimizing the costs for installing level 2 and 3 chargers.

Economic implications of the electrification of all or subsets of the vehicles in town is presented in Table 9.

Electrification	Capital Costs	NPV	\$/kWh/yr
Full EV	\$2,136,000	-\$675,307	-\$3.09
Tribal SUVs	\$120,000	\$362,641	\$5.51
ATVs	\$460,000	\$263,582	\$7.53
Tribal + ATVs	\$590,000	\$513,950	\$6.79

Table 9. Cost of electrification of all and subsets of the vehicles in the community

4.4 Economic Modeling Assumptions

Table 10 displays the economic inputs that were used in the study.

Economic Input	Source	Value	Units
<i>All Dollar Values in the Study are 2023 \$</i>			
General Inputs			
Real Discount Rate (adjusted for inflation)	Department of Energy Life-cycle costing rate. Also, rate used by Alaska Energy Authority for Renewable Energy Fund analysis.	3.0%	per year
General Inflation Rate (used when Nominal economic values were required)	Report of the President's Economic Advisors.	2.3%	per year
Analysis Period	Life of the Wind Turbine.	25	years
Initial Fuel Prices			
AVEC Diesel Price	AVEC spreadsheet for 12/31/2022	\$4.15	per gallon
Residential Heating Oil Price	City fuel price on Feb 23, 2023.	\$8.32	per gallon
School and Water Treatment Plant Heating Oil Price	37.5% less than Residential price, based on a recent audit of the Water Treatment plant.	\$5.20	per gallon
Gasoline Price	City fuel price on Feb 23, 2023.	\$8.32	per gallon
Fuel Price Escalation Rates			
AVEC Utility Diesel	HOMER limitation	0.00%	per year
Residential / School / Water Treatment Plant Heating Oil	EIA Annual Energy Outlook 2023	-0.28%	per year
Gasoline	EIA Annual Energy Outlook 2023	-0.06%	per year
	Rates calculated from the EIA Annual Energy Outlook are across the period 2023 - 2048 for the Pacific Region		

Table 10. Economic inputs

All dollar values in the study are 2023 inflation-adjusted dollars. The price escalation rates in the above table are also real rates (inflation-adjusted). For example, a -1% escalation rate means that the price will increase 1% less than general inflation. Many of the rates in the table are negative because energy prices in 2023 were relatively high and expected to decline in the short term.

4.5 Federal Tax Credit for Wind Energy and Electric Vehicles

The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) introduced an investment and production tax credit on renewable energy projects, including wind. Through the IRA's Investment Tax Credit (ITC), projects that start construction by Dec. 31, 2024 can receive up to a 30% tax credit on the cost of installed equipment [16]. Projects can also receive up to 10 percentage points of bonus credits if it either meets domestic content threshold or locates facilities in fossil-fuel-dependent "energy communities". In 2025 these tax credits will be converted into emissions-based, technology-neutral tax credits available to all types of power facilities with zero or net-negative carbon emissions.

The Internal Revenue Service (IRS) provides a \$7,500 tax credit via the Commercial Clean Vehicle Credit for any new electric commercial vehicle that meets qualifications [17].

These tax credits were applied in the post-modeling as a sensitivity analysis. By applying these tax credits to the capital cost of the wind turbine, BESS and EVs the total overhead of the project can be significantly reduced.

5 Results

The modeling tool HOMER provides several output metrics that allow a comparison of the different use scenarios and price sensitivities. In this section the most important metrics are presented and discussed.

5.1 Economic Results

The economic benefits and costs of each of the project elements were evaluated. Table 11 summarizes the results. There are three numeric columns in the table. The “Capital Cost” column in the table shows the upfront capital required to fund each project element. The “Net Present Value” column shows the net sum of all benefits (primarily fuel savings) and costs (including capital costs) resulting from the project; benefits and costs are time-discounted so that the total is a present value figure. Any value greater than zero indicates a cost-effective project. The “Benefit / Cost Ratio” is an alternative measure for expressing the cost-effectiveness of a project element (and leads to the same economic conclusion as using net present value). It expresses the benefits of the project, net of operating costs (capital costs not included), divided by the initial capital cost. Cost-effective projects have benefit-to-cost ratios greater than 1.0, indicating benefits exceed the capital cost on a present value basis.

Project Component	Capital Cost	Net Present Value	Benefit / Cost Ratio
Wind Turbine + BESS	\$10,680,000	-\$7,061,461	0.34
Tribal EV + ATVs	\$590,000	\$513,950	1.87
Residential Electric Heating	\$1,857,233	\$2,030,387	2.09
TOTAL:	\$13,127,233	-\$4,517,124	0.66

Table 11. Base Economic Results

There are three project elements addressed in the table. First, the addition of the 1-MW wind turbine and battery system are evaluated and compared to the reference case that has only diesel generation. The “Net Present Value” column shows that this project element loses money on a present value basis—the capital and operating costs of the wind turbine and batteries are more than the reduction in AVEC fuel cost. The loss is \$6.7 million. However, this element of the project enables additional investments, addressed below, so economic conclusions cannot be reached before evaluating the additional project components. Also note that no federal tax credits or grant funding were included in this analysis.

The wind turbine / battery component provides opportunities for other potentially cost-effective projects because the generation of the wind turbine often exceeds the utility electric load and the ability of the battery to store more energy. Our analysis determined that the most valuable use of that excess generation was to convert Tribal SUVs and ATVs in the community to electric vehicles, and then to charge those vehicles with a combination of excess wind generation and additional diesel generation. Having already accounted for the costs of the wind turbine / battery project element, the costs of the EV project element only needed to account for the additional costs of the electric vehicles and charging equipment. The benefits of the EVs are saved gasoline and maintenance, and benefits outweigh costs by about \$514,000 on a present value basis. This helps to offset some of the \$6.7 million loss generated by the wind turbine / battery investment.

The other project component that was found to be cost-effective was serving residential heating loads through electric thermal storage heaters controlled to only operate when excess wind is available. That project addition contributed another \$2.0 million of net benefit.

However, in total, the full set of project components come short of being economically justified, yielding \$4.5 million less benefits than total capital and operating costs, on a present value basis. The resulting benefit-to-cost ratio is 0.66, shy of the 1.0 threshold.

A couple of sensitivity analyses were done. First, the projects were evaluated assuming the wind/battery component

received a 30% federal investment tax credit, and the two Tribal SUVs each received \$7,500 federal EV rebates. These credits were modeled as reducing the capital costs of those project components, and the economic results are shown in Table 12.

Project Component	Capital Cost	Net Present Value	Benefit / Cost Ratio
Wind Turbine + BESS	\$7,476,000	-\$3,857,461	0.48
Tribal EV + ATVs	\$575,000	\$528,950	1.92
Residential Electric Heating	\$1,857,233	\$2,030,387	2.09
TOTAL:	\$9,908,233	-\$1,298,124	0.87

Table 12. Economic results including Federal Tax Credit sensitivity

The project bundle is still short by \$1.3 million net present value and lands at a 0.87 benefit to cost ratio.

The next sensitivity analysis assumes that future bulk fuel storage investments and operating costs would be avoided by the project investments. The scenario first presumes that the fuel prices stated in the Economic Assumptions section of this report and used in the base case analysis do not include any bulk fuel storage costs, often because those costs have been covered by Federal and State investment. Next, the sensitivity case assumes that AVEC diesel, heating fuel oil, and vehicle gasoline fuel reduction will reduce the need for bulk fuel storage and will soon translate into avoided bulk fuel storage investments. Using average bulk fuel storage capital and operating cost data from the Alaska Energy Authority, bulk fuel storage amounts to a cost of \$2.88 / gallon of fuel used¹. This cost was added to the base case fuel cost for AVEC diesel, heating oil, and gasoline when doing the economic analysis of this sensitivity scenario. The results of this analysis, which do not include investment tax credits, are presented in Table 13.

Project Component	Capital Cost	Net Present Value	Benefit / Cost Ratio
Wind Turbine + BESS	\$10,680,000	-\$3,934,207	0.63
Tribal EV + ATVs	\$590,000	\$942,039	2.60
Residential Electric Heating	\$1,857,233	\$3,521,288	2.90
TOTAL:	\$13,127,233	\$529,120	1.04

Table 13. Economic results including Avoided Bulk Fuel Storage Costs

This avoided fuel cost addition brought the project bundle to a cost-effective net present value of \$0.5 million and benefit-to-cost ratio of 1.04. Finally, the prior two sensitivity conditions were analyzed together. Both federal tax credits and avoided bulk fuel storage cost were combined into a scenario and the results are presented in Table 14.

¹Capital cost, operating cost, and typical storage volume data sourced from a phone conversation between the American Economic Association and Deerstone Consulting. Conversion of this data was done by co-author Alan Mitchell using further assumptions about discount rate and life of fuel tank.

Project Component	Capital Cost	Net Present Value	Benefit / Cost Ratio
Wind Turbine + BESS	\$7,476,000	-\$730,207	0.90
Tribal EV + ATVs	\$575,000	\$957,039	2.66
Residential Electric Heating	\$1,857,233	\$3,521,288	2.90
TOTAL:	\$9,908,233	\$3,748,120	1.38

Table 14. Economic results including Federal Tax Credit and avoid bulk fuel storage costs

The project bundle under these assumptions is cost-effective, generating \$3.7 million of net present value and having a benefit-to-cost ratio of 1.38.

No social cost of carbon emissions was considered in any of these economic analyses. The imposition of a carbon tax would further improve the economic return of these projects.

5.2 Uses of Wind Generation

Figure 1 shows how the wind generation is utilized in the final package of projects. The total wind generation averages 257 kW across the year. On average, 107 kW or 42% of the production is used by the AVEC electric utility system to reduce diesel generation. Of the remaining wind generation, 9 kW of the remaining wind generation is used to support charging EVs in the community, although additional diesel generation is also needed for EV charging. 116 kW of the wind generation is used to power the retrofit electric heating systems for residential buildings. This leaves a net 25 kW of wind resource that must be curtailed and not used for useful purposes.

Uses of Wind Generation, average kW

Figure 1. Wind generation utilization chart

6 Conclusion

Large 1-MW wind turbines can be cost effective in larger rural communities in Alaska such as St. Mary's and Stebbins, although the economics become much more challenging in many of the smaller communities. The difference is primarily the size of the electric load, which is larger for these bigger communities, partly because many of them are intertied to another village. The size of a small community's electric load limits how much of the high-cost electricity can be displaced by a relatively large wind turbine's output. This case study shows the potential for excess renewable energy generation to be used economically to power electrified heating and transportation if those loads can be dispatched to take advantage of the excess and are chosen to minimize installation costs while maximizing community fuel savings. There is additional potential for a large economic benefit if a renewable energy system is able to meaningfully reduce the need for additional bulk fuel storage facilities.

A number of uses for the excess wind generation were evaluated. When compared by the amount of NPV benefit provided per unit of consumed excess wind generation, vehicle electrification was the most valuable, followed by controlled electric heating of residential buildings. These were the only two uses of excess generation which were found to add more fuel saving benefit than the cost of implementing the use.

When evaluating electric heating systems, it was found that systems that only utilize excess generation maximized NPV, as they don't require expensive electric utility upgrades to operate. Two residential electrical heating systems gave the best results: a system that uses plug-in electric heaters controlled via wireless LoRaWAN (long-range wide area network) Smart Plugs, and electric thermal storage heaters controlled by AVEC through a power line carrier or mesh wireless technology. The thermal storage heater solution was selected as the best choice due to the untested nature of the LoRaWAN Smart Plug solution. The best residential electric heating systems had robust positive economics, when evaluated as incremental additions to a wind turbine/battery investment. The thermal storage heater solution had a capital cost of \$1.9 million but delivered \$2.3 million of NPV benefits beyond cost recovery. Overall, five different residential electric heating systems showed positive NPV, indicating they would create economic benefit if utilized. However when evaluating one-off, non-residential systems, it was found that high installation costs lead to poor economics. As such, both the school and water treatment plant electric heating retrofits were not cost-effective.

Vehicle electrification implementing electric tribal SUVs and ATVs uses a small amount of the excess electricity. However it has approximately \$500,000 of net present benefits, primarily because of the relative efficiency differences between gas and electric vehicles in these use cases. In other words, even with purely diesel generation, these particular EVs would provide benefits. It should be noted that electric vehicles that heat occupied cabins (cars and trucks) are less relatively efficient compared to gas vehicles than those that don't (ATVs, snow machines) due to waste heat from the internal combustion engine of gas vehicles being available for this heating. Low daily/yearly mileage EVs in extreme cold environments are also less likely to offer cost benefits over higher daily/yearly mileage vehicles due to energy used while parked to heat the battery to prevent damage. This effect means that snow machines, which are only used seasonally in the winter, might not be as beneficial to switch to electric than ATVs and higher mileage cars and trucks, like the tribal SUVs. EVs may reach purchase cost parity with conventional vehicles in the near future. At that point the benefits of switching to electric vehicles will be even greater. One caveat is that we did not model the availability of EVs to charge when excess wind was available. Most household vehicles are driven less than a few miles a day and should be available to be plugged in to a charger to accept this excess energy assuming that chargers are generally available at the place they are parked in sufficient quantity for the vehicles parked. Fleet vehicles, such as the tribal SUVs are assumed to be on the road a larger percentage of the time and may not be as available to charge as modeled by the HOMER deferrable load module. This may decrease the benefit modeled. However, existing technologies such as vehicle to grid capabilities that allow EVs to discharge as well as charge may increase their potential, essentially turning them into mobile grid batteries.

Capital cost can be significantly reduced by utilizing the ITC provided by the IRA, specifically the capital cost of integrating the wind turbine into the community's electric grid. Capital costs of acquiring electric vehicles can also be reduced with the IRS's commercial vehicle tax credit. Members of the community seeking to replace their gas vehicles with electric can benefit from the IRS's clean vehicle tax credit [18]. When bundled with avoided bulk fuel storage costs, a greater amount of overhead costs can be mitigated.

Grid stability is not investigated by HOMER, which only looks at energy matching between loads and resources. With such a large wind turbine, a higher power BESS or other strategy may be necessary to prevent grid destabilization by frequency or voltage deviation. One such strategy long employed by AVEC is a ‘secondary load controller’ or electric boiler in the powerhouse that can respond quickly to changes in wind output and prevent harmful levels of generation and load mismatch. AVEC has found, however, that the EWT wind turbine has responsive curtailment abilities that can help with grid stability. Unmanaged EV charging also has the potential to negatively impact grid stability [19], but EV charging has the potential to be used as a resource to increase grid stability by reacting quickly to load and wind generation changes, either through quickly communicated control commands to ramp power up or down or through grid-supportive capabilities of the chargers themselves (an NREL paper discusses the economics of adding these capabilities to end loads with a circuit that can respond to grid deviations and control loads without any external communications [20])

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Appendix A Supplemental Information

Figure A.1. Fuel curve of the 236KW Generator

Figure A.2. Fuel curve of the 360KW Generator

Wind speed [m/s]	Power [kW]	Cp [-]
0 - 2.5	0	-
3.0	12	0.249
3.5	25	0.326
4.0	41	0.354
4.5	62	0.381
5.0	92	0.412
5.5	133	0.446
6.0	181	0.468
6.5	231	0.470
7.0	289	0.471
7.5	356	0.472
8.0	432	0.472
8.5	518	0.472
9.0	597	0.459
9.5	668	0.436
10.0	732	0.410
10.5	796	0.385
11.0	853	0.359
11.5	905	0.333
12.0	941	0.305
12.5	973	0.279
13.0	992	0.253
13.5	998	0.227
14.0	1000	0.204
14.5	1000	0.184
15 - 25	1000	0.166 - 0.036

Figure A.3. Power curve of the EWT wind turbine